

MEDICAL SCIENCES

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF IMPLANT ABUTMENTS USED IN DENTAL IMPLANT TREATMENT

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Abstract

Dental implant treatment has become a standard procedure for treating edentulous patients. Advances in technology have simplified treatment protocols; however, treatment planning remains the most critical and complex aspect. This article examines the advantages and disadvantages of various types of dental implant abutments and aims to provide clarity in selecting this essential component of implant therapy.

Keywords: dental implant, abutment, CAD/CAM, dentistry, prosthetic treatment

Introduction: The advancement of technology has led to significant progress in dental medicine. CAD/CAM technologies, intraoral scanning, and digitally guided implantology have made previously challenging procedures both accessible and popular, overcoming the limitations posed by outdated equipment.

In recent years, dental implant therapy has become a routine procedure. Despite the facilitation provided by specialized dental software, clinicians must meticulously plan and analyze every aspect of implant placement and subsequent prosthetic restoration. Particular emphasis is placed on the selection of prosthetic components upon which the final structures are mounted.

The dental implant abutment serves as the critical connecting link between the implant and the crown [1].

The aim of this literature review is to analyze the various types of implant abutments used in prosthetic treatments involving dental implants.

Titanium Abutments

Titanium abutments are regarded as the "gold standard" for application in all areas of the oral cavity [2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. The first prosthetic abutments (original Branemark abutment) were hollow cylinders with an internal hexagon and a fixation screw.

The commercial market offers a wide variety of implant abutments, with each manufacturer adopting its own standardized type of abutment available in several variations.

In the literature [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13,14], they are generally classified as:

- Temporary abutments
- Permanent abutments (prefabricated and customized).

Prefabricated (standard) Abutments

Temporary standard abutments can be made of titanium, polymethyl methacrylate, or polyetheretherketone. These abutments allow for clinical customization to create an optimal design for the peri-implant mucosa. Permanent prefabricated abutments, on the other hand, can undergo modifications through reduction or reshaping.

Permanent prefabricated abutments are most commonly manufactured from titanium alloy but can also

be made from zirconium dioxide. Standardized titanium abutments are the most widely used due to their ease of application and lower cost compared to other types [15, 16]. They are available in several standardized variations based on height, size, and shape.

Factory-produced abutments can be either straight or angled, with the angulation typically limited to a few options, most commonly 15 and 20 degrees. Modifications are often necessary to adapt the abutments as closely as possible to the specific clinical case. The height and width of the transmucosal portion are also predefined by the manufacturer in several variations.

Standard abutments can be designed with a gingival margin or without one, depending on the clinical needs.

Titanium Bases

Titanium bases are a type of prefabricated abutment with a specific geometric design, used in CAD/CAM technology for the fabrication of metal-free definitive restorations. These bases are also standardized in terms of diameter, height, and the dimensions of the transmucosal zone. They can be straight or angled.

The use of titanium bases allows for achieving a higher aesthetic outcome, making them a preferred choice in the anterior and premolar regions. Some authors highlight their advantages over zirconia abutments, which are associated with weaker connections and greater susceptibility to fracture [15, 17, 18, 19].

Another advantage of titanium bases is their extraoral adhesive fixation to the prosthetic restoration. This process enables precise control over excess cement around the implant superstructure, a critical factor in reducing peri-implant complications [20, 21, 22, 23].

Permanent Customized Abutments

This type of abutment can be fabricated from titanium alloy, zirconium dioxide, lithium disilicate, or a combination of different materials (known as hybrid abutments).

Characteristics of Customized Abutments

Customized abutments can be classified by the material used in their fabrication. They may be entirely titanium, zirconia, or a combination of titanium and other materials, referred to as hybrid abutments. Tita-

nium customized abutments are milled entirely from titanium alloy, while hybrid abutments combine a titanium base with an adhesively bonded aesthetic material (zirconium dioxide or lithium disilicate). This aesthetic component mimics the shape of a tooth stump and transmucosally replicates the architecture of the peri-implant mucosal tissue (PIMT). In the literature, the aesthetic component of the hybrid abutment is often referred to as the "mesoabutment."

The use of hybrid abutments aims to combine the advantages of titanium and zirconia abutments while eliminating their respective drawbacks [24]. Some authors suggest PEEK (polyetheretherketone) as a material for permanent prosthetics, arguing that it reduces the risk of implant overload and minimizes wear on adjacent teeth [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

The concept of Virtual Abutment Design (VAD), a part of CAD technology, is based on the idea that the shape of the abutment should be determined by the morphology of the restoration it will support [31].

As early as 1996, Marchack [32] presented a clinical case involving the prosthetic restoration of an upper central incisor using a customized titanium abutment. He noted several advantages of customized abutments over standardized ones. According to Marchack and other authors, customized abutments can eliminate many of the complications observed with prosthetic treatments that use prefabricated abutments [32, 33, 34, 35, 36].

The main advantages of customized abutments, as described in the literature, are:

- Creation of an optimally precise connection with the implant [37];
- Elimination or reduction of unfavorable implant angulation;
- Adequate compensation for the interdental space of the defect;
- Creation and maintenance of the design of the peri-implant mucosa [38, 39];
- Optimal transmission of chewing forces to the implant and surrounding periodontal tissues.

According to some authors, implant-supported individualized abutments can serve as a means to model the soft tissues around the restoration. Tselios et al. [40] utilize temporary individualized abutments, milled using CAD/CAM technology, in immediate implant prosthetics in the anterior region, with which they shape a better emergence profile and model the peri-implant mucosa. This approach eliminates subsequent aesthetic complications and leads to stable, predictable clinical outcomes. This protocol has also been described in other publications [41].

Other authors [42, 43] apply individualized abutments in cases where there are anatomical limitations, such as insufficient clearance from the antagonist and large interproximal spaces. Individualized abutments are also used in cases where parallelism between the individual implants involved in a common restoration cannot be achieved [44].

According to Tripodakis et al. and Furhauser et al. [45, 46], individualized abutments replicate the emer-

gence profile of the natural tooth with maximal precision, eliminating the possibility of over-contouring the entire superstructure caused by the volumetric cylindrical cross-section of the standardized abutment and the thickness of the definitive prosthetic restoration. Parpaiola and Yildirim et al. [47, 48] emphasize the risk of peri-implantitis as a complication due to the deep marginal edge of the standardized implant abutment and residual cement subgingivally, which can lead to bone loss and an unsatisfactory treatment outcome.

Comparative Characteristics of Different Types of Abutments

A number of studies highlight the thickness of the mucosa as an important characteristic for aesthetics, particularly in the anterior region [32, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59]. One of the significant disadvantages of permanent titanium alloy abutments is the greying of the peri-implant mucosal tissue (PIMT) caused by their color [32, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65]. To eliminate this drawback, zirconium dioxide abutments have been introduced into clinical practice.

Due to their colour, ceramic abutments are considered more suitable for restorations in the aesthetic zone [66], although other authors have found that the thickness of the gingiva is a leading factor, regardless of the abutment colour [17]. According to Sailer et al. [17], a thickness of attached gingiva less than 2 mm compromises aesthetics for both types of individualized abutments.

According to Smith and Turkyilmaz [7], zirconium dioxide abutments are not recommended as the first choice unless high aesthetics in the anterior region are the primary goal. The authors emphasize that their application should be limited due to the greater micro-crack formation and the potential for micro-leakage at the implant-abutment interface. Similar concerns are raised regarding individualized titanium abutments, which leads to the conclusion that standardized abutments are optimally applied in all areas of the oral cavity.

On the other hand, Yuzugullu and Avci [67] report that the vertical micro-crack in titanium and zirconium CAD/CAM abutments is similar, ranging from 2.5 to 3.2 μm , which is comparable to that observed in factory-made abutments. In contrast, Lopes et al. [68] express a different view, finding better accuracy in standardized abutments.

Micro-movement can often be a cause of fracture in zirconium dioxide abutments at the implant-abutment interface. For this reason, R. Kelly [69] recommends the use of titanium bases, which reduce the possibility of fractures and micro-leakage.

Fatigue and the risk of fractures are significant complications in implant prosthetic treatment. Foong et al. [70] investigate the fatigue of titanium alloy and zirconium dioxide abutments and determine that fatigue is greater in the latter. According to their findings, the failure rate is directly dependent on the material type and the design of the abutment.

The survival of zirconium dioxide abutments can be influenced by the manufacturing method, the thickness of the abutment, and the position of the implant.

According to several *in vitro* studies, zirconium dioxide abutments are more prone to fractures compared to those made of titanium alloy [2, 71, 72, 73]. Lin et al. [38] define the connection between titanium implants and zirconium abutments as unsatisfactory, which has been confirmed by other studies as well [74].

In their *in vitro* study, Stimmelmayer et al. [75] analyze wear resistance under electron microscopy and find that zirconium abutments exhibit 10 times higher values than titanium abutments.

The application of hybrid abutments aims to combine the advantages of titanium and zirconium abutments while eliminating their disadvantages.

Elsayed et al. [15] subjected implant superstructures made of lithium disilicate to fatigue testing. The team applied dynamic loading of 1.2 million chewing cycles and found fractures only in the zirconium dioxide abutment group.

In another study [76], the authors note the limited application of hybrid abutments solely in the anterior region due to the risk of fractures in distal areas.

Various laboratory studies report a high survival rate for test specimens with titanium abutments, while others report a 43.8% failure rate when testing the same superstructures [55, 15, 77].

The creation of an individualized design for the transmucosal part and positioning of the margin preparation in individualized implant abutments is used as a tool to prevent complications resulting from residual cement in the subgingival area, which can lead to inflammatory changes in the soft tissues and negatively affect the prosthetic treatment [78]. Korsch and Walther [79] clinically investigate metal factory-made and individualized abutments in single implant restorations and find a 0% loosening of the fixing screw with individualized abutments and 7.7% with standardized ones. Hosseini et al. [80] compare single implant abutments made of zirconium dioxide with prosthetic restorations of the same material and metal abutments with metal-ceramic crowns in the premolar region based on biological, mechanical, and aesthetic criteria. The results show no significant difference in the parameters studied. No colour change in the peri-implant gingiva was observed, and patient feedback indicates no aesthetic difference between the materials, although professional aesthetic assessments noted such differences.

Sailer et al. [63] also compare individualized zirconium dioxide and titanium abutments based on the characteristics mentioned above and find no significant difference between the two materials. The authors report that more plaque was found on structures with zirconium dioxide abutments. Zembic et al. [81] reach the same conclusion after investigating the same criteria over a three-year period.

Bosch et al. [82] compare the biomechanical behavior of zirconium dioxide implant superstructures and metal-ceramic crowns with titanium abutments. They conclude that both studied groups exhibit similar qualities, with statistically insignificant differences in the evaluated parameters. In their publication, Otero et al. [83], supported by Rompen et al. [84], conclude that individualized abutments with a concave profile have a positive effect on the stability of peri-implant mucosal

tissue (PIMT). Bompolaki et al. [42] report a higher number of functional complications with implant superstructures featuring factory-made abutments compared to hybrid abutments with lithium disilicate.

According to Schepke et al. [85], the advantages of individualized over factory-made abutments remain unclear. The team compared standardized and individualized zirconium abutments and found no statistically significant differences over a one-year period. Long et al. [86] express the opinion that individualized abutments, milled using CAD/CAM technology, exhibit good survival rates compared to conventional abutments.

Our laboratory studies on fatigue and fracture resistance show twice the mechanical strength in implant superstructures, which are a combination of monolithic zirconium dioxide and a titanium base, compared to individualized titanium abutments with the same type of crown [87]. The same test groups were subjected to clinical examination to assess their biomechanical behavior. The results demonstrated excellent survival rates for all types of abutments but also highlighted the previously mentioned advantages of individualized titanium alloy abutments [88].

Conclusion: The selection of the appropriate implant abutment based on the individual characteristics of each patient is a leading factor in achieving high aesthetic outcomes. Prosthetic treatment with a correctly chosen abutment ensures functional stability and is directly linked to maintaining the soft tissue profile and aesthetics.

Despite the trend towards unifying and standardizing prosthetic treatments, factory-made solutions often fail to meet the individual needs and personal requirements of each patient. In some clinical cases, the standard abutment cannot provide the optimal positioning for the future restoration and gingival architecture.

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